

Radargrammetry DEM Generation using High-resolution SAR Imagery over La Palma during the 2021 Cumbre Vieja Volcanic Eruption

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Abstract— This letter aims at investigating the potential of high-resolution (up to 0.7 by 0.5 m²) Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images in generating Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) using the radargrammetry technique. In this work we process two SAR images recorded by the Capella Space X-band satellite-borne radar sensor on two consecutive days, October 2 and 3 2021, over La Palma (Canary Islands, Spain) during the Cumbre Vieja volcanic eruption. We adopt an iterative point-aggregation algorithm to identify matching pixels between the two images, then the height estimation is performed using a distance minimization routine over the previously identified pairs of matching points. The resultant radargrammetric DEM is validated against a lidar-based DEM for various land cover classes, showing a good agreement in the areas less affected by lava flow. An estimation of the lava thickness is performed, yielding profiles of the cone area, which are compared to the photogrammetry estimates obtained from the Pléiades mission data.

Index Terms—Radargrammetry, Digital Elevation Model, high-resolution synthetic aperture radar, 3D mapping, lava thickness, micro-satellite SAR.

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital Elevation Models are a widely used tool to study the Earth's surface for several applications, including volcano monitoring. Radar images, collected by spaceborne SAR sensors, have demonstrated a good potential in generating DEMs, and the all-weather cloud-penetrating capability of such technology is increasingly relevant for DEM applications [1]. Three-dimensional maps can be extracted from SAR data by means of few different techniques, such as interferometry and radargrammetry [1]-[7]. Interferometry exploits the phase difference between two SAR images collected with a spatial baseline, whereas radargrammetry employs the disparity between two SAR amplitude images [5]. Generally, interferometric techniques have shown a higher accuracy, but suffer from phase unwrapping errors due to temporal decorrelation of the radar scatterers. On the other hand, amplitude-based radargrammetry is more robust against atmospheric disturbance and presence of gas particles in the air, including volcanic emissions, but is affected by speckle noise [1]. This decorrelation source is mitigated by spatial filtering, which in turn worsens the spatial resolution, and decreases the

density of the point cloud that generates the radargrammetric DEM. However, the availability of high-resolution SAR images, e.g. collected by the recently launched Capella Space SAR mission, makes viable the generation of accurate radargrammetric DEMs, even after the resolution loss due to the spatial filtering. Capella Space is a new satellite constellation being part of the recent availability of micro- and nano-satellites with Earth observation capabilities. Capella satellites mount an X-band radar sensor, achieving a spatial resolution of 0.7 by 0.5 m² in Spotlight mode [7]. The analysed case study is located in the south-west part of La Palma (Canary Islands, Spain), affected by the Cumbre Vieja volcanic eruption, which started on 19th September 2021 and ended on 13th December 2021, with a maximum volcanic explosivity index (VEI) of 3. The eruption caused the evacuation of more than 7000 people, due to the ejection of volcanic gases, pyroclastic material and lava flow, which covers an area larger than 1200 hectares reaching the ocean to form two lava deltas. The length of the lava flows is greater than 6.5 km (subaerial) and 1.1 km (submarine) [8]. SAR imaging techniques have been employed in the past to monitor volcanic activity, including the study of the topography changes due to the lava flow: SAR data and derived products are now fully included as tools for volcanic hazard monitoring systems [9][10]. The main contribution of this work is an investigation of the potential of high-resolution SAR images in generating good quality DEMs using the radargrammetry technique as a viable alternative to other surveying techniques, such as photogrammetry and interferometry. The radargrammetric DEM is validated against a high-precision DEM generated using a lidar sensor before the 2021 Cumbre Vieja eruption over the areas not affected by lava flow. An estimation of the thickness of the lava covering some portions of the area under study is performed.

II. DATASET DESCRIPTION

The map in Fig.1 shows the case area, together with the geographical extension of the lava flow due to the Cumbre Vieja eruption. The terrain elevation ranges roughly from 0 to 2000 m, with a mix of bare soil, cultivated and forested land,

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and the lava flow has an average height of 12 m, reaching a maximum of 80 m [8]. The two analysed Single Look Complex (SLC) SAR images were collected by the Capella Space-3 SAR sensor on October 2 (master image) and 3 (slave image), 2021. The radar works at X-band (9.65 GHz), Spotlight mode, HH polarization, same-side looking antennas. The satellite orbit is descending, at an altitude of about 500 km, 191° azimuth angle. The pixel spacing is 0.7 m in range (rg.) and 0.5 m in azimuth (az.), the image extension is about 7.2 km (rg.) x 6 km (az.). The look angle was about 33° for image 1 and 29.5° for image 2, giving a convergence angle of about 4°: such a small value is expected to yield good matching performance, but it may increase the height estimation error. The images were multi-looked with a window of 3-by-3, yielding a rg. and az. pixel spacings of about 2.1 m and 1.5 m, respectively. A slightly different azimuth sampling causes a slightly different size between the two images (Fig.2), that is corrected by resampling the slave image.

Fig. 1 – Analyzed area, with a layer indicating the extension of the lava flow, provided by the Copernicus EMS Rapid Mapping service (<https://emergency.copernicus.eu/EMSR546>). Colour scale indicates the dates of the lava flows, from Sep 20 (dark red) to Dec 17, 2021 (white). The area delimited in yellow marks the footprint of the analysed SAR images.

Fig. 2 – SAR amplitude images recorded by the Capella Space on-board sensor over La Palma on 2nd (a) and 3rd (b) October, 2021, with the cone area marked in red. SAR data (c) 2021 Capella Space all rights reserved.

III. METHODOLOGY

The DEM generation was performed by the following processing steps: (i) image extraction, (ii) resampling of the slave image, (iii) speckle filtering (multi-looked), (iv) image matching, (v) height estimation, (vi) spatial interpolation and smoothing, (vii) geocoding. A basic sketch of the radargrammetry principle used for the height estimation is

shown in Fig. 3, where M and S denote the master and slave satellites, P is one point on the Earth surface, h its height; r_1 and r_2 are the ranges between the point P and the M and S satellites, respectively; and θ_1 and θ_2 are the M and S look angles, respectively. Once known the positions of the M and S and the values of r_1 and r_2 , the intersection between the two rays would give the location of the point P and its height. However, the intersection between two rays is not guaranteed in the three-dimensional space, due to the presence of disturbance in the data and misalignment, thus the DEM generation technique should look for homologous points in the M and S images. The two pillars of the radargrammetric technique implemented are the *image matching* and *height estimation*.

Fig. 3 – Radargrammetry principle

A. Image Matching

This stage identifies the couples of matching points, which are likely to be associated to the same area on the Earth surface, by searching for pixels with high coherence across the two images. This operation is realized using a *point aggregation* algorithm, which recursively forms a set of pixel couples (PCs), using as input a set of 10-20 seed points that are selected manually after a visual examination as high-energy stable scatterers. The algorithm works as follows: (i) starting from one seed PC, candidate points in the M and S image are selected moving along the cardinal directions within a maximum search distance ($d_{S,max}$), which means that the number of candidate points increases with $d_{S,max}$; (ii) for each candidate PC (P_M, P_S), the LxL matrices containing their surrounding points are constructed, respectively I_M and I_S ; (iii) the normalized 2D cross-correlation between I_M and I_S is computed, using a subpixel factor of 8. This spatial cross-correlation is computed using its formulation in the Fourier domain, accounting for the subpixel factor, and is normalized upon the product of the average intensities of I_M and I_S . (iv) if such correlation value is higher than a predefined threshold, λ , the candidate PC is selected as seed point. This sequence of steps yields a new set of seed points, for a further iteration. The point aggregation is repeated iteratively until the increase in the number of selected points is negligible. In this work, three iterations of the matching routine were launched, by progressively refining the search area and increasing the minimum point correlation. The main algorithm parameters for each of the three iterations were set as following: iteration 1, $d_{S,max} = 10 \text{ pixels}$, $\lambda = 0.1$; iteration 2, $d_{S,max} = 5 \text{ pixels}$, $\lambda = 0.3$; iteration 3, $d_{S,max} = 3 \text{ pixels}$, $\lambda = 0.5$. The size of the spatial cross-correlation window was set at 32x32 pixels.

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B. Height Estimation.

The height estimation is performed for each couple of matching points by finding the value of h that minimizes the Euclidean distance between the points identified in the M and S images. Let us start from one couple of matching points identified on the master, $P_1 = [l_1, c_1]$, and slave, $P_2 = [l_2, c_2]$, images, where l is the row index and c is the column index. The position of P_1 is given by $\mathbf{p}_1(\tilde{h}) = [x_1, y_1, z_1]$, whereas $\mathbf{p}_2(\tilde{h}) = [x_2, y_2, z_2]$ is the position of P_2 . We do not assume that the two points have identical coordinates, which would yield only three unknowns. Instead, we hypothesize that the two points have different coordinates, which gives two systems of non-linear equations with three unknowns each. For P_1 , the vector $\mathbf{p}_1(\tilde{h})$ is forced to satisfy the range, Doppler and ellipsoid equations for satellite SAR acquisition geometries, which are respectively the first, second and third equations of (1) [1,6,11]:

$$\begin{cases} \|\mathbf{p}_1(\tilde{h}) - \mathbf{p}_M\| = r_1 \\ (\mathbf{p}_1(\tilde{h}) - \mathbf{p}_M) \cdot \dot{\mathbf{p}}_M = 0 \\ x_1^2/(a_1 + \tilde{h})^2 + y_1^2/(a_1 + \tilde{h})^2 + z_1^2/(b_1 + \tilde{h})^2 = 1 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where the position of the satellite for the master acquisition is \mathbf{p}_M and $\dot{\mathbf{p}}_M$ is its velocity. These two quantities are extracted using l_1 , the radar and SAR acquisition geometry parameters, and the interpolated satellite orbit trajectory, whereas the range r_1 is computed from the column index c_1 [1,6,11]. The nonlinear system (1) is solved numerically using the golden section search method [12]. The system of equations to compute $\mathbf{p}_2(\tilde{h})$ is identical to (1), replacing the subscript ‘1’ with ‘2’, and ‘S’ with ‘M’. The ellipsoid parameters a_i, b_i are calculated using the World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84) reference system. The height estimation is performed by bounding the height values within $[h_{min}, h_{max}]$, whose values are set by evaluating an available DEM, and setting a maximum distance, d_{max} , between $\mathbf{p}_1(\tilde{h})$ and $\mathbf{p}_2(\tilde{h})$ as described in the following.

Algorithm Height Estimation

<p>for $\tilde{h} \in [h_{min}, h_{max}]$:</p> <p> solve system (1) for P_1 and extract $\mathbf{p}_1(\tilde{h})$</p> <p> solve system (1) for P_2 and extract $\mathbf{p}_2(\tilde{h})$</p> <p> compute Euclidean distance $d(\tilde{h}) = \ \mathbf{p}_1(\tilde{h}) - \mathbf{p}_2(\tilde{h})\$</p> <p> extract \hat{h} that minimizes $d(\tilde{h})$, $\hat{h} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\tilde{h}} \{\ \mathbf{p}_1(\tilde{h}) - \mathbf{p}_2(\tilde{h})\ \}$</p> <p>if $d(\hat{h}) < d_{max}$: return \hat{h} else: discard points P_1 and P_2</p>

For this case study, we set $h_{min} = 0$, $h_{max} = 2000$ m, $d_{max} = 1.5$ m. The set of points with associated height estimates form an elevation pattern point cloud, that is interpolated using a standard triangular interpolation network method to obtain the radargrammetric DEM.

IV. RESULTS

The elevation pattern point cloud obtained is shown in Fig.4. We observe that the coverage of the point cloud is not spatially uniform: from a cross-comparison between this result and the terrain properties, most of the gaps seem to concern areas with high slopes and dense vegetation. The complicate geometry of high-slope areas and the low coherence of vegetated areas typically hinder the performance of the matching algorithm in radargrammetry [3]. The obtained DEM is shown in Fig.5.

Fig. 4 - Radargrammetry-based elevation pattern point cloud.

Fig. 5 - Radargrammetry DEM.

A. Validation

The radargrammetric DEM was validated against a DEM generated by an airborne lidar sensor, provided by the Spanish National Geographic Institute (IGN). The lidar DEM was recorded in 2016 using a Leica ALS60 sensor, with a minimum resolution of 0.5 points per m^2 and a root mean square error (RMSE) in elevation of 0.2 m (<https://pnoa.ign.es/estado-del-proyecto-lidar/segunda-cobertura>). We computed the DEM deviation (D_{DEM}) between the radargrammetric DEM and the lidar DEM, on the area not affected by the lava flow (to the right of the black-dashed line in Fig.5). The accuracy of DEMs is typically affected by factors that decrease the coherence of SAR image pairs, such as presence of vegetation and different types of land cover (LC), and critical geometries, i.e. high terrain slopes, that increase the height estimation error. An accurate validation should perform the statistical analysis of the D_{DEM} by considering these factors, [4][6][13], thus the following statistics of the D_{DEM} were computed: mean (μ), standard deviation (σ), skewness (γ), and excess kurtosis (κ_e). The parameters γ and κ_e quantify the affinity between the D_{DEM} distribution and the Gaussian one, which is usually considered as an indicator of the absence of outliers and of a systematic source of errors in the examined DEM [13]. The correlation coefficients between D_{DEM} and the terrain height ($\rho_{D,H}$) and slope ($\rho_{D,S}$) were also computed. Table I contains the value of the statistics for the whole dataset and for different LC classes, i.e. cultivated land, coniferous forest, natural grassland and bare rock (maps provided by the Copernicus European Rapid Mapping Products). The data show an overall offset of about

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28.9 m, which was corrected in the final stage, and a σ of 8.4 m. The normalized 2D distribution of D_{DEM} is shown in correlation with the height and slope values in Fig.6 a and b, respectively. The 2D distribution of the D_{DEM} versus the terrain slope is shown for four different LC classes in Fig.7. Results show a quite good robustness against slope and height, as D_{DEM} exhibits very low correlation with the height and slope values, also noticeable from the flat behaviour of the 2D distributions in Fig.6 a-b. Forested areas are concerned by higher values of the $\rho_{D,H}$ and $\rho_{D,S}$, more significant deviations from the Gaussian distribution and higher dispersion of the D_{DEM} values (Fig.7c), which is probably due to the loss of coherence caused by vegetation. Cultivated land and bare rock areas seem to show a higher robustness and smaller dispersion of the D_{DEM} values: they have low values of γ and κ_e , whereas the highest ones are presented by the forest class. The overall value of γ is 0.48, suggesting a low asymmetry of the D_{DEM} distribution. The overall κ_e (5.08) results heavily biased by the poorly performing classes. The theoretical height accuracy σ_h can be calculated from the range resolution σ_r and the look angles θ_1 and θ_2 [1],

$$\sigma_h = \sigma_r (\sin^2 \theta_1 + \sin^2 \theta_2)^{1/2} / \sin(\theta_1 - \theta_2) \quad (2)$$

where the σ_r is calculated considering the multilook and subpixel factors, $\theta_1 \approx 33^\circ$ and $\theta_2 \approx 29.5^\circ$, yielding σ_h of about 3.15 m. This value is lower than the σ of D_{DEM} in Table I, but of the same order of magnitude. This discrepancy may be due to multiple noise sources present in real data degrading the image matching and height estimation performance.

TABLE I: STATISTICS OF DEM DEVIATION

LC Class	μ	σ	γ	κ_e	$\rho_{D,H}$	$\rho_{D,S}$
All	28.9	8.4	0.48	5.08	0.18	0.11
No Class	28.1	7.8	0.81	7.2	0.08	-0.15
Cultivated land	30.6	6.4	-0.18	1.15	0.04	0.14
Coniferous forest	26.5	8.9	1.18	6.49	0.18	0.13
Natural grassland	31.3	8.2	0.47	6.91	0.02	0.04
Bare rock	27.3	7.1	0.35	1.29	0.25	0.09

Fig. 6 – D_{DEM} distribution vs height (a) and slope (b). For each figure, the red line denotes the linear fit to the normalized 2D density.

A. Lava Thickness

The lava thickness was estimated subtracting the lidar-based DEM from the obtained radar DEM. Similarly, the lava thickness estimates available at [14] were obtained subtracting

Fig. 7 - D_{DEM} distribution vs slope for bare rock(a), natural grassland(b), coniferous forest (c), cultivated land (d) classes. Color scale as in Fig. 6b.

the same lidar DEM from the photogrammetric DEM by processing the optical images recorded by the Pleiades sensor on October 2, 2021, with a ground resolution of 2-by-2 m².

The two lava thickness estimates are compared (Fig.8) over the area affected by the lava flow (reported in Fig.1). Fig.8 shows the cone area on the Eastern side, which gradually turns into lava flow moving Westward. The normalized histograms of the lava thickness estimates are shown in Fig.9. In the lava flow area, the photogrammetric product presents, as expected, a more uniform distribution, whereas the radar product has larger fluctuations, also evident in the lava thickness profile in Fig.10a. The radar estimate (Fig.8a) seems to reproduce the cone shape more accurately compared to the photo one (Fig.8b). As shown in the lava thickness profile (Fig.10b), the radar-based thickness estimate reaches values of 70-80 m, that match the field survey data available in [8], whereas the photo-based estimate has maxima of about 30-40 m. This disparity can be due to the presence of volcanic gases and ashes in the cone area, that deteriorate the performance of the optical sensor, while their effect on radar data is limited. In fact, on October 2, the eruption showed strombolian activity with simultaneous explosions and ejection of ashes and gases [8]. We observe that the photo DEM has on average higher values than the radar DEM, also evident from the normalized histograms in Fig.9. The radar DEM presents a higher concentration of values smaller than 5 m (probably concerning the lava flow area), and higher distribution tails (probably characterized by the thickness estimate in the cone area). The disparity in the lava flow area may be due to the different temporal interval between the radar and photo acquisitions, and to a performance decrease suffered from the radar product, which can be explained by a coherence loss due to the non-stationarity of the scene within the interval separating the two SAR acquisitions (one day). The presence of this bias should also be considered in the evaluation of the cone area. Another factor that may affect the accuracy of the radar DEM is that the ash plume creates a Doppler modulation in the radar signal [15] that may deteriorate the performance of the matching and height estimation.

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Fig. 8 – Estimates of the lava thickness using radargrammetric DEM (a) and photogrammetric DEM based on Pleiades data (b). The red and white arrows denote the directions of the lava profile plots in Fig. 10.

Fig. 9. Normalized histograms of the radar and photo DEMs.

Fig. 10. Lava thickness profiles of radar and photo DEMs at the locations indicated by the red (a) and white (b, cone area) arrows in Fig. 8.

V. FINAL REMARKS

This letter has presented an investigation about the potential of high-resolution SAR imagery in producing radargrammetric DEMs, as an alternative to radar interferometry and photogrammetry. SAR interferometry requires quasi-identical incidence angles and different spatial baselines and, similarly to photogrammetry, suffers from the presence of volcanic gases and ashes, which are common during a volcanic eruption. Hence, radargrammetry may be a valid solution during emergency situations to produce good estimates of the lava thickness, especially in the cone area. Radargrammetry would benefit from shorter revisit times, which would enable implementing multi-image techniques and refinement [1]-[6]. The recent flourishing of micro- and nano-satellite SAR missions with increasingly higher coverage and shorter revisit times may well allow an efficient monitoring of the lava flow through radargrammetry.

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